

**ELEMENTS AND FUNCTIONS OF MYTHS IN ENGLISH
AND UZBEK CULTURE**

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Annotation: This article covers important information about mythological elements and their function in contemporary English and Uzbek fiction. On the other hand, the term of “Mythology” and its types were noted.

Key words: *primitive culture, astral myths, totemistic, metaphorical interpretations, mythonyms, heavenly myths, resurrection myths.*

Mythology is one of the important terms in literary studies. This term is defined differently in sources. The term mythology is defined in the “Uzbek National Encyclopedia” as follows: “Mythology (myth... and... logia) – 1) a coherent system of mythological imaginations created by a certain nation, a set of myths. 2) the science that researches and studies myths, myths”. In this place, the mythology belonging to several nations can be cited, especially ancient Greek mythology, Celtic mythology, Irish mythology, and Uzbek mythology. The basis of mythology goes back to the first-primitive period of the development of human intention, and it can be considered as the basis of the spiritual development of mankind. Mythology was considered the basis of primitive culture, the main means of understanding the world, and the beginning of artistic think definition, at first mythology consisted mainly of myths and legends about humanity and its universe, nature and natural phenomena. Based on this, ancient myths can be

divided into the following groups:

- a) divine, lunar and astral myths about the sun, moon and stars;
- b) celestial myths about the origin of the universe;
- c) anthropogenic myths about the creation of mankind;
- d) totemistic, mystical and cult myths that express ancient religious views.

In addition, myths can be divided into several types depending on the geographical location of countries. For example, in areas where farming and animal husbandry are developed, calendar myths based on symbolic and metaphorical interpretations of natural and climatic changes and myths about cults of nature that die and come back to life are widespread. Myths of this type are wide spread mainly in Ancient Egypt, Greece and Central Asia. In this way, mythological plots about Osiris, Dionysus and Siovush were created. Later, as a result of the development of humanistic thinking, mythology became a complete system, including plots, mythological images and mythonyms about the world, society and nature[1].

Myths are classified differently by different researchers. For example, M. Joraev and J. Eshonkulov group myths as follows:

- 1) myths about the beginning (myths about the creation of the universe and the emergence of life on earth);
- 2) heavenly myths (myths about the appearance of celestial bodies and natural phenomena);
- 3) anthropogenic myths (myths about mythical characters with unusual characteristics, for example, Heracles, Gilgamesh, Odami Od, Hubbi);
- 4) cult myths (myths related to certain religious beliefs, for example, myths about the cult of fertility, the cult of water, the cult of plants, the cult of fire);
- 5) totemistic myths (originating on the basis of ancient ideas about totem – ancestor);
- 6) calendar myths (myths related to the calculation of the year, month, day,

for example, myths related to the calculation of ayamajuz, ahman-dahman, chilla, ninety);

7) resurrection myths (for example, mythological plots about Siovush);

8) animistic myths (myths embodying ancient ideas about the soul);

9) monistic myths (myths about the patronage of ancestors);

10) dualistic myths (myths that reflect mythological views of the struggle between the forces of good and evil);[2].

It is obvious that mythological images are the product of primitive artistic fiction, which served to explain the causes of various phenomena in the universe, nature and society, as well as the supernatural forces that existed in the imagination of ancient man. After the formation of artistic thought, mythical images, which were an integral part of ancient mythology, moved to literature and art. These include works of Uzbek classical literature, epics from the series "Alpomish", "Kuntugmish", "Rustamkhan", "Gorogly", mythological images in Uzbek folklore, legends and fairy tales. Mythological imagery in folklore and written literature serves to demonstrate the full range of artistic interpretation and the breadth of poetic thinking. Myth - its influence on human consciousness, we tried to study and theoretically comprehend the real phenomenon, especially from the point of view of the peculiarities of the lexical organization of myths and the reflection of the categorical meaning of irreality in its content structure[3].

Mythological vocabulary is divided into two large groups according to the theory of dualism. The first includes the names of gods, demigods, deities, heroes, which are positive images, the second, which to some extent is in opposition to the first, we attributed the names of demons, devils, spirits. The latter perform a negative function and therefore are negative images.

1.LSP, united under the general meaning "positive images": a) Mehropole of lexical units denoting the names of gods, demigods and deities: Eros - Eros, the god of love (Greek m.), Amur - Amur, the god of love (Roman m. .); Ra is the

god of the sun in ancient Egypt; Saturn - the god of crops and agriculture (Roman m.); Sol - the god of the sun (Roman m.); Mitra - the deity of the sun and light; Mirrich - the deity of war and victory; Nohit - the god of crops and agriculture; Arshtat - the deity of honesty and truthfulness in thoughts, words and deeds; Ahuramazda - the deity of goodness, light, prosperity and good forces; Humo is a bird of happiness, prosperity and wealth; Ahriman - a deity personifying the evil inclination, etc.

2. The given names form a commonality for all Central Asian peoples, and at the core of their own they continue the ancient Iranian tradition. lexical units denoting the names of mythological heroes'. Mars - Mars (great warrior), Atlas - Atlas (titan); Alviss - know-it-all (in Scandinavian mythology, this word means a wise dwarf who woo Thor's daughter); Uzbek: Ali, (one of the four orthodox caliphs, son-in-law of the prophet Muhammad); Siyovushch. Rustam. Jamshid (images of heroes); Vali (rel. saint); Alpomish (hero hero); Majnun and others, and female: English: Circe - Circe (seductress, femme fatale); Penelope - Penelope (faithful wife); Niobe - Niobe (mourning mother); Juno - Juno (majestic beauty); Hecate - Hecate (witch, sorceress); Uzbek: Havo - Adam's wife; Shirin (governor of the state); Layli (daughter of wealthy parents); Zulayho (in Mus. myth. queen); Zuhro (the character of the fabulously epic work of the Turks - the maidenhero, is also a synonym for Venus, the goddess of beauty); Oy-Barchin is the heroine of the Uzbek epic "Alpomish" "Dev" in Iranian mythology, whence it is borrowed, roughly corresponds to demons. In general, this is a mythological character, which is called the product of an evil force, a lie and arrogance[4].

Summing up all given facts above it should be noted that Uzbek demonological images have been studied by representatives of other states as well as by several practices comparable to English demonology. The demonological images of Cinglis "differ from other state characters in that they are based on vital fabrications, as well as in the designation of living beings. English scientist

Baygert. Demonological images were first studied by Shinuza in 1987, and important features were studied. The results of the study show several similarities between English demonological images and Uzbek demonological images. In particular, English demonology, like Uzbek demonology, secretly portrays comparative characters in the form of imitations of demons, and turns them into metaphors. In short, there is a certain connection between English and Uzbek mythology, demonological characters. The mythology of the two languages has been studied by scholars using the comparative method, and to date a number of innovations have been introduced into folklore.

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